

HANDS ON WITH IIIF: A PILLAR IN DIGITAL PRESERVATION

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Abstract - This workshop will introduce the IIIF Image and Presentation standards and include hands-on exercises to create and use off the shelf tools to get started. We will discuss how to set up a IIIF system in production with a small collection and how to scale up to millions of images. We will include a discussion on the wider IIIF community and sources of help and advice going forward.

Attendees will leave the session with an understanding of the different IIIF standards and what choices need to be looked at when setting up a IIIF system. No prior knowledge of IIIF is required and the core sessions should be easily accessible to those with confidence using the Web.

Attendees will need to bring a laptop and images to work with. These can be open access images from your collections or personal photographs you are happy to share.

Submission Type - Please select 1 submission type: Workshop.

Keywords - IIIF, Digital Content, Interoperability, Digital Libraries, .

Conference Topics - Please select 1 conference topic: Tūhono - Connect.

I. INTRODUCTION: ABOUT IIIF

The International Image Interoperability Framework (IIIF) [1] is a set of open standards for delivering high-quality, attributed digital objects online at scale. It's also an international community developing and implementing the IIIF APIs. IIIF is backed by a consortium of leading cultural institutions and a global and engaged community [2].

IIIF is a way to standardize the delivery of images and audio/visual files from servers to different environments on the Web where they can then be viewed and interacted with in many ways.

Modern Web browsers understand how to display formats like .jpg and .mp4 at defined sizes, but cannot do much else. The IIIF specifications align with general Web standards that define how all browsers work to enable richer functionality beyond viewing an image or audio/visual files. For images, that means enabling deep zoom, comparison, structure (i.e., for an object such as a book, structure = page order) and annotation. For audio/visual materials, that means being able to deliver complex structures (such as several reels of film that make up a single movie) along with things like captions, transcriptions/translations, annotations, and more.

IIIF makes these objects work in a consistent way. That enables portability across viewers, the ability to connect and unite materials across institutional boundaries, and more. This portability is one of the reasons IIIF is an important standard in digital humanities research allowing open access collections to be used as research data and for research software to be written once and used with many collections.

IIIF is driven by six API specifications [3], which include the two core APIs (Image and Presentation) and four additional APIs (Authorization Flow, Change Discovery, Content Search), and Content State). Multiple IIIF viewers [4] have been created to take advantage of the universe of IIIF resources, each with different features and benefits.

II. INTENDED AUDIENCE

The workshop is open to anyone and has been delivered in the past to attendees at multiple levels of technical ability. The workshop will be accompanied by an online workbook with step-by-step instructions so everyone can keep up with the hands-on exercises. There are plenty of opportunities for attendees to ask questions and to cover topics in detail if people are interested in technical details.

III. TOPICS

This workshop will address the following topics:

- Information Management Science
- Knowledge Creation and Dissemination
- Digital Humanities and Cultural Heritage
- Human-Computer Interaction in Digital Libraries
- Information Retrieval

IV. EXPECTED OUTCOMES

By the end of the workshop participants should have IIIF images and manifests to work with. They will have experienced using manifests in multiple tools and will have a good understanding of how the IIIF APIs function and the benefits of using them.

V. CONCLUSION

The IIIF standards and APIs supports digital preservation by enabling the high-quality, interoperable delivery of digital objects, making them accessible and usable across platforms and institutions. Implementation of IIIF can optimize storage strategies by delivering accessible versions of digital assets (images, a/v, 3D) while storing high-resolution masters in cost-effective locations. This approach balances cost efficiency with preservation, ensuring that digital assets remain accessible for detailed exploration while maintaining data integrity.

The broader IIIF community intersects with that of the digital preservation community and fosters and exchange of knowledge and best practices. This workshop, in exposing the iPres community to a hand-on IIIF experience, will provide context for including IIIF in broader digital preservation solutions.

REFERENCES

- [1] About IIIF. <https://iiif.io/>
- [2] IIIF Community. <https://iiif.io/community/>
- [3] API Specifications. <https://iiif.io/api/index.html>
- [4] IIIF Viewers. <https://iiif.io/get-started/iiif-viewers/>

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHIES

Glen Robson is the IIIF Technical Coordinator of the IIIF Consortium. He coordinates the maintenance of the IIIF specifications, supporting the IIIF community infrastructure and aiding early implementers of IIIF. He runs regular online training sessions attended by participants around the world and also in person workshops in Canada, UK and Australia.

Martin R. Kalfatovic is Managing Director of the IIIF Consortium this role. His remit is to expand use of the IIIF standard and APIs, grow participation in the IIIF Consortium, and enhance the global user experience of digital objects across all formats, including images, audio-visual, and 3D.

Caitlin Perry is IIIF's Communications and Community Coordinator, working with experts and adopters of IIIF to advance the framework and its utility. Before IIIF, Caitlin served as Communications and Data Manager at Educopia Institute, providing communications support, data management, and event planning across a portfolio of programs and research projects.

